

FEATURES OF THE SECOND MEDIA ERA

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Abstract.

In this study, the differences and peculiarities of the new media environment that emerged as a result of the penetration of the Internet into the information exchange process were highlighted.

Keywords.

new media, traditional media, internet, public space

Annotation.

This study touched on the difference and specifics of the new media environment from the traditional media environment caused by the penetration of the internet into the information exchange process.

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The world is wounded that humanity, struggling to dominate nature with technological innovations and developments, is constantly striving to discover and innovate. As a result of these efforts, the emergence and increasing development of new technologies has also influenced the process of Information human exchange. The Internet, which has become an integral part of our lives among the new media, has become popular all over the world as an information exchange platform. With the Internet, people have been able to obtain information in many areas in an easy, cheap, fast and safe form (5, 223)

Since 1992, the widespread use of Internet technology by individuals has expanded the use of the internet. The change and development of digital technologies in the internet drum accelerated the flow of sound, image, text and information. An important reason for the so-called "new media age" of the 2000s is the general public orientation of technological change (6, 233). The new media was built on the basis of the Internet and became a whole, along with digital technologies. The development of the Internet and information technology with

great speed affected the form and content of the media. As a result, new media and traditional media concepts came to the fore.

American philosopher Mark Poster found a link between capitalism and new media as a result of his research. He emphasizes traditional media as the "first media age", stating that in this period of Central, one-sided dialogue and state control, participants have characteristics characteristic of a passive audience. Describes the "second media age" as having a democratic character based on decentralized, bilateral and multi-directional communication, free from state interference (7, 3). Poster defines users as active individuals (7, 3-4), focusing on the fact that the element of interoperability is in the forefront in the new media era.

In a traditional media environment, gatekeepers (gatekeeping) decide for themselves which content can be transmitted to an audience. The order of content and its presentation in Radio, television and newspapers is determined by media managers and editorial executives (4, 97-139). In traditional media, materials that the editor-in-chief deems important are placed on the page.

Geray cites the following 3 main features that distinguish new media and traditional media:

Interactivity (Interactive): interactivity is the most basic character of new media. This is the presence of ambivalence in the communication of the media with the audience. Information is the simultaneous interfacing of the transmitter and receiver (2, 18-19). Williams (11, 180) discusses new media in terms of interactivity, stating that these boundaries have been removed intact through new media technologies. If we look at the general characteristics of all media before the new media era, we will witness that communication is presented unilaterally (9, 878). In New Media, individuals can be both content creators and content recipients.

Ommassification (Demassification): it allows the exchange of information separately with each individual in groups of a wide audience (2, 18-19). In traditional media, where news and speeches are presented for multiple individuals, communication in New Media is carried out without the provision of mass perception. Due to the high cost of traditional media, the news and information given through it was aimed at a larger audience rather than a single person or small audience. Personal communication opportunities have increased in the new media environment. There has been an appeal to an individual different from traditional media.

Timelessness: new media gave a person the ability to transmit and receive information at any time. This feature of new media eliminated the necessity that it was in "the moment"(2, 18-19). In relation to the information transmitted to the

general public in traditional media, the audience did not have the ability to express opinions on the spot. The interactivity of the new media allowed the information to be transmitted and received without any time and space that the recipient wanted to comment on the information presented to him. For example, a message can be read on any Watt and from anywhere, as well as leave comments on it.

According to Linda Weiser Friedman and Hershey Friedman (1, 9-4), new media has five key features-communication, collaboration, community, creativity, and convergence. In the new media, the communication process is fast and through the internet. New media technologies will create a new public space in collaboration with the audience through the internet. The teams created on this field are equal and inclusive. On the new media platform, the user has the right to freely express his opinion. In addition, users are creative in nature and can simultaneously produce content, share and reproduce existing content. The final convergence property is the most important force of the new media. The convergence principle brought traditional media into the new media environment by combining it with telecommunications and computer systems.

Gönenli and Hürmeriç address the features of new media participation, openness, conversation, community, connection and cooperation, commenting as follows (3, 215):

Participation: in the new media space, the feedback of each interested person is taken into account and able to participate in the mass communication process.

Openness: in New Media, it is open to the audience to comment and participate in discussions. New media encourages voting, comment, and information sharing. It does not allow the obstacles encountered in the creation and transmission of content.

Conversation: while traditional media deals with the transmission and distribution of content to the target audience, a two-way dialogue is created in New Media.

Society: New media has allowed society to communicate quickly and efficiently. In this space, individuals with the same interests and views can come together and exchange ideas on different topics.

Connectivity: new media is building strength by using other web pages, resources, and links.

Collaboration: individuals can come together in the virtual world, develop shared ideas in collaboration, and implement them in a virtual environment.

In conclusion, the penetration of its technologies into the field of informatization forced traditional media to move to a new platform. Therefore, the

media brought new features to the middle. The new media environment in which we live today has accelerated the novelty value and flow of information more than ever.

In the traditional media era, there were two separate categories of producer (information producer) and consumer (information receiver), which could not change these statuses over a longer period of time. In the age of new media, they achieved the ability to fulfill the task of one another. That is, the former status of only information transmitter or only information receiver changed to proconsumer status. There was also a mutual dialogue between the informant and the information receiver. The concept of time and space in the era of traditional media has lost its importance. The monopolization of information and the ban on it were put to an end. The new media literally turned into a democratic public space.

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